

ACADE - an automatic mesh generation and adaptation framework for viscous flow

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Abstract

The current work proposes an end-to-end framework, namely ACADE, for unstructured mesh generation and adaptation in the context of viscous flow simulation. Starting from a surface mesh, ACADE is capable to generate unstructured inviscid volume mesh as well as semi-structured boundary layer mesh in an automatic way. Based on subsequent CFD simulation results, metric based mesh adaptation can be performed along with or independent from boundary layers for flow feature capturing. The boundary layer mesh generation and adaptation capacity are demonstrated on the classical Onera M6 and the CRM configuration from NASA high-lifting workshop.

1 Introduction

For discretization methods, e.g. finite element or finite volume, to yield reliable numerical simulations, an explicit oversight of the involved approximations is a must. Since there is no beforehand (a priori) techniques to manage approximation errors in complex problems, it is necessary to use a posteriori methods in combination with adaptive discretization strategies [refs]. As a result, adaptive meshing becomes essential for accurately simulating challenging cases, such as flow problems with highly anisotropic solutions, which can only be detected and represented through a posteriori anisotropic adaptation [refs]. Moreover, certain situations call for the use of highly anisotropic elements (with aspect ratios exceeding 1000) in specific regions, requiring that these elements maintain a semi-structured arrangement throughout the mesh adaptation process. This study focuses in particular on viscous flows featuring boundary layers that develop near solid surfaces, as seen in wall-bounded flows.

In the context of viscous flow simulation, semi-structured Boundary Layer (BL) mesh is key for more accurate evaluation of quantities of interest. A common method to construct such meshes, namely advancing layer method, inflates the unstructured surface mesh on no-slip walls into the volume along the local surface normals as a stack of layers. Such technique, which was developed more than two decades ago [4,6]. More recent endeavor consists in smoother viscous layer to inviscid mesh transition [8] and more robust automation process [7,10].

Given the complexity of viscous flow characteristics, especially under high Reynolds and/or Mach number conditions, a priori defined surface mesh based BL mesh may not be suitable for flow feature capturing, e.g. shock. BL mesh adaptation techniques are accordingly developed for sequential [11] and parallel [12] applications. However, different from tetrahedron-composed inviscid volume mesh, semi-structured BL mesh involves different element types, including prism, pyramid and tetrahedron. As a consequence, rich set of local mesh operations are necessary to perform refinement and/or definement.

In the present work, we propose an end-to-end framework, namely ACADE, for unstructured mesh generation and adaptation in the context of viscous flow simulation. Based on robust normal computation considering multi-normal situations, BL mesh can be constructed in an automatic way from a user-provided surface mesh. As for mesh adaptation, instead of local volume mesh modification, an adaptive remeshing approach, which only involves local surface mesh modification, is proposed. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that open-source solutions are leverage for the current framework development for the purpose of ensuring its applicability. The effectiveness of ACADE, is demonstrated on the Onera M6 and a CRM configuration.

The paper is organized as follows. We present at first the BL mesh generation technique with an emphasis on normal computation. Then the metric based mesh adaptation and remeshing details are provided. After summarizing the overall algorithm, empirical validation tests are conducted on Onera M6 and CRM configurations in the context of viscous flow simulation.

2 Technological bases

2.1 Boundary layer generation

Boundary layer generation consists in inflating the surfacing mesh into the volume along the local surface normals. In the current study, the so-called open advancing-layer approach is adopted to avoid complementary linear elastic computation involved within its closed advancing-layer counterpart [9]. BL mesh generation starts by computing local surface normal. Despite the advocacy of using analytic surface normal instead of relying on the discrete surface [Connell 1995], the availability of geometrical surface is not always ensured. Moreover, averaging computation is still necessary at patch intersections. As a result, normal computation is most commonly performed on discretized surface mesh. In the present study, an iterative approach is applied to calculate the so-called 'most normal' normal [1]. In order to reduce the number of invalid elements, we pre-process the given normals and predict the volume of elements. For each invalid element found, we attempt to collapse the normals until no more negative element is found. Further local adjustment is performed based on element quality and manifold check. In addition, the outer surface mesh of BL should be solely composed by triangle elements for subsequent inviscid volume mesh generation and adaptation. Pyramid elements are accordingly added to address local layer gap.

2.2 Metric based mesh adaptation

Mesh adaptation can be performed with or without BL mesh in the present framework. For the purpose of solely adapting inviscid volume mesh, BL mesh is kept constant, and mmg tool [2] is leveraged for metric based isotropic adaptation. When adapting with BL mesh, a metric based volume mesh adaptation is performed with mmg tool at first without considering BL mesh. Then a new BL mesh is constructed from the newly adapted no-slip surface mesh via the process described in the previous section. Finally, gmsh [5] is used for inviscid volume mesh reconstruction based on the background metric field. We refer to [2] for more details of general volume mesh adaptation technique. In this section, we focus on presenting the metric computation as well as adaptation process with BL mesh.

2.2.1 Isotropic metric

Following the study of [3], the L_∞ norm of the interpolation error $(u - \Pi_n u)$ with respect to a quantity of interest u on a tetrahedron element K is bounded by the following relationship,

$$\|u - \Pi_n u\|_{\infty, K} \leq c_d \max_{x \in K} \max_{\vec{e} \in E_K} \langle \vec{e}, |H_u(x)| \vec{e} \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where E_K is the set of edges of K , c_d is a constant, and H_u is the hessian matrix of u . By assuming that it exists a metric tensor $\overline{M}(K)$ such that:

$$\max_{x \in K} \langle \vec{e}, |H_u(x)| \vec{e} \rangle \leq \langle \vec{e}, \overline{M}(K) \vec{e} \rangle, \forall \vec{e} \in E_K, \quad (2)$$

the interpolation error ε_K on K is given by:

$$\varepsilon_K = c \max_{\vec{e} \in E_K} \langle \vec{e}, \overline{M}(K) \vec{e} \rangle. \quad (3)$$

The metric distribution should be constructed so that the interpolation error is more evenly distributed. Let ε denote the maximal error level tolerated on the mesh. The mesh edge length should be like:

$$\varepsilon = c \langle \vec{e}, \overline{M}(K) \vec{e} \rangle, \forall \vec{e} \in E_K. \quad (4)$$

Introducing the desired metric tensor $M = \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \overline{M}$, Eq.4 leads to

$$\langle \vec{e}, M(K) \vec{e} \rangle = 1, \forall \vec{e} \in E_K. \quad (5)$$

While in [3], M is an anisotropic tensor, which allows defining the edge length independently in the three principle directions, M is proportional to the identity matrix for isotropic metric, which changes the element size uniformly in different directions. The isotropic version of M , adopted in the present study, is expressed as follows,

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\lambda} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{\lambda} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tilde{\lambda} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\tilde{\lambda} = \tilde{\lambda}_1 \tilde{\lambda}_2 \tilde{\lambda}_3, \quad (7)$$

and

$$\tilde{\lambda}_i = \min \left(\max \left(\frac{c \cdot (\lambda_i)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\varepsilon}, \frac{1}{h_{max}^2} \right), \frac{1}{h_{min}^2} \right). \quad (8)$$

λ_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are the three eigenvalues of the hessian matrix. It is worth mentioning that the physical quantities evolve brutally in the normal direction to the no-slip surface within BL. As a consequence, instead of using a single eigenvalue, e.g. the maximal one, the cubic root of the three $\tilde{\lambda}_i$ is taken as an averaged metric, so that the local gradient in the directions parallel to the surface is taken into account.

2.2.2 Adaptation with boundary layer mesh

When the volume mesh is adapted with BL mesh, an adaptation-remeshing process is adopted to avoid specific local mesh operations on semi-structured element. More concretely, after each CFD simulation, the metric field with respect to the selected physical quantity is calculated via Eq.8. The volume mesh, BL elements of which are tessellated at first, is then adapted based on this metric field without considering the presence of BL mesh with mmg tool. We adapt the whole volume mesh instead of the no-slip surface mesh so that the flow features, which are not apparent on the surface, can be captured. After the adaptation, the new no-slip surface mesh is used to construct a new BL mesh. Tetrahedron mesh generation is preformed via Gmsh based on the previously computed background metric field to close the iteration. Current Gmsh technical portefolio only supports isotropic background metric. That is why only isotropic metric is considered in the present study. If one adapts only the inviscid mesh within the current framework, anisotropic metric field support is a straightforward extension thanks to mmg tool.

2.3 Overall algorithm

Figure 1: Overall mesh adaptation algorithm.

3 Numerical results

Numerical results are presented here to demonstrate the basic characteristics of approach described in this work. Two configurations, namely Onera M6 and CRM, are accordingly chosen. The numerical tests on Onera M6 configuration, which are under transonic condition, is twofold. Firstly, the volume mesh is adapted with BL mesh with respect to the static pressure field for the purpose of surface

Figure 2: Illustration of the mesh adaptation process including both boundary layer and tetrahedra volume mesh on the Onera M6 wing configuration with respect to shock positions in the context of viscous flow simulation. Wing surface mesh (a) at initial state, (b) after three adaptation cycles, (c) after six cycles, (d) after nine cycles.

shock capturing. Secondly, the adapted mesh is further adapted in the inviscid part for better shock and wake description. As for CRM, the test is preformed under subsonic condition. Inviscid volume mesh is adapted for wake vortex capturing.

3.1 Numerical set-up

SU2 flow solver is applied for RANS CFD simulations. Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel (JST) scheme is used for convective flux discretization. The turbulence is modeled by the Spalart-Allmaras(SA) model. Centered with the in-house developed BL mesh generation tool, mesh adaptation and generation are performed respectively with mmg tool and Gmsh. A modified version of the open-source metric computation tool Mshmet [ref] is used for metric computation.

3.2 Viscous Onera M6

The ONERA M6 wing is a classic validation case. Air enters the wind tunnel at transonic speed and is accelerated over the wing to a supersonic speed causing a shock to appear on the wing. The free-stream Mach number is 0.84 and the angle of attack is 3.06° .

Figure 3: Shock description on the Onera wing surface during the mesh adaptation process in the context of viscous flow simulation. Pressure field on the wing surface (a) at initial state, (b) after three adaptation cycles, (c) after six cycles, (d) after nine cycles.

3.2.1 Adaptation with boundary layer

As mentioned, a twofold adaptation is performed on the M6 configuration. Firstly, a surface mesh is taken as input, and the corresponding volume mesh is generated with BL mesh following the procedure described in Fig.1. 9 adaptation cycles are performed in total. The CFL number of the CFD simulation at the initial iteration is set to be 30 and it takes roughly 800 iterations to a converged state. Then 200 iterations, initiated by the simulation result of the previous cycle, are performed for each subsequent cycle. The surface mesh adaptive process is illustrated in Fig.2, while the corresponding static pressure field is depicted in Fig.3. The surface pressure contours (along with surface meshes in Fig.2) show that the mesh is refined in the shock region and the shape of the so-called 'lambda' shock is clearly captured. The mesh away from the shock is coarsened, due to a low variation in pressure in those regions. The surface pressure contours become sharper and more regular with adaptivity.

The evolution of total element number during the adaptation process is illustrated in Fig.4 (a). It can be seen that the element number stagnates after three cycles, which means that in the last six cycles the mesh is adapted in the direction to average element-wise interpolation without changing the overall element number. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that after nine cycles, the total element number is reduced compared to the initial mesh, which further demonstrates the benefit of adaptive mesh.

Figure 4: Evolution of node number during the mesh adaptation (a) with BL mesh, (b) without BL mesh.

Figure 5: Illustration of tetrahedra volume mesh adaptation with respect to Mach number field description on the Onera M6 wing configuration. Cross section mesh (a) at initial state, (b) after three adaptation cycles, (c) after six cycles, (d) after nine cycles.

3.2.2 Adaptation without boundary layer

Following the first adaptation process, 9 adaptation cycles are performed with respect to Mach number field keeping the BL mesh constant. The CFD resolution iteration settings are identical to the first part of adaptation. Evolutions of mesh and Mach number on a cross section are illustrated in Fig.5 and 6. The inviscid volume mesh is adapted to capture the sharp changes of Mach number, i.e. shock and wake, regions. At the end of the adaptation process, not only the shock but also the wing tip vortex in the wake region (see Fig.7) are clearly captured.

The node number evolution during the adaptation process is illustrated in Fig.4 (b). Even though mesh adapted for shock capturing tends to stagnate in the last cycles (see Fig.6 (c) and (d)), the mesh at the rear of the wing keeps adapting for better wake depiction. Consequently, different from the first part (Fig.4)(a), in inviscid volume mesh adaptation, after the sharp increase in the first cycles, the increase, which slows down, does not stop even till the last conducted cycle.

Figure 6: Mach number description on the cross section (a) at initial state, (b) after three iterations, (c) after six cycles, (d) after nine cycles.

Figure 7: Mach number description in the wake region (a) at initial state, (b) after three adaptation cycles, (c) after six cycles, (d) after nine cycles.

3.3 Viscous CRM

The CRM configuration, which corresponds to the first case in the fifth high lift prediction workshop (HLPW-5), is used to further demonstrate BL mesh generation and volume mesh adaptation capacity of ACADE. A relatively coarse surface mesh is taken as the input for the sake of illustration, given the substantial amount of elements required for quantitative CFD analysis. BL mesh constructed on the input surface mesh is depicted in Fig.8 and 9. Thanks to the current implemented normal computation as well as BL generation algorithms, the surface mesh is smoothly dilated towards the inside of the volume, even at the wing-fuselage joint (see Fig.9(b, c)). The volume mesh with BL built on the initial surface mesh leads to 1491999 nodes and 3732116 elements.

For the CRM configuration, the free-stream Mach number is 0.2 and the angle of attack is 11.0° . The CFL number is set to be 20 and 2000 iterations are performed on the initial mesh. Subsequent CFD simulations, initiated by the previous cycle result, run with 500 iterations. The node elements of the four adaptive meshes are respectively 1655918, 1971859, 2151168, 2264313. Similar as the inviscid volume mesh adaptation on the M6 configuration, after a sharp increase at the first two

cycles, the node number increase slows down but not stagnates afterwards for wake capturing.

The wake meshes on two different sections at the beginning and end of the adaptation process are illustrated in Fig.10 colored by the Mach number field. The two sections are located at respectively $y = 50$ and 60 m, while the center of the aircraft is approximately at $y = 11m$. The wake description is much clearer after adaptation on the first section and the mesh is adapted with respect to the wake morphology. On the second section, the wake cannot be fully captured on the initial mesh, which is adapted uniformly in the cuboid region at the rear of the aircraft. The adaptive mesh captures the full wake feature, while coarsens the region elsewhere. The adaptive mesh after 4 cycles around the airfoil is depicted in Fig.11. The mesh is adapted on the upper side of the wing. In addition, the zoom at the leading and the trailing edge of the airfoil further illustrate the BL mesh constructed on the initial surface mesh.

Figure 8: Illustration of boundary layer mesh on the CRM configuration at (a) fuselage, (b) head of the aircraft, (c) tail of the aircraft.

Figure 9: Boundary layer mesh illustration of the CRM configuration; (a) global view from the rear of the aircraft wing, (b) zoom at the wing fuselage joint from inside, (c) zoom at the wing fuselage joint from outside.

Figure 10: Illustration of tetrahedra volume mesh adaptation process on the CRM configuration. Wake Mach number and mesh at $y = 50\text{m}$ (a) at initial state, (b) after four adaptive iterations; wake Mach number and mesh at $y = 60\text{m}$ (c) at initial state, (d) after four adaptive iterations.

4 Discussion

In the first part of adaptation on the M6 configuration, despite a well-adapted surface mesh, the volume mesh does not seem to evolve to capture the shock-induced pressure change (see Fig.5 (a)). As described in Fig.1, when adapting with BL, an adaptation-remeshing process is conducted. The volume mesh is firstly adapted based on the computed metric without considering BL mesh, then a new inviscid volume mesh is built within the same metric defined on the background mesh from the new BL mesh. The adaptive mesh after the two steps in the ninth adaptation cycle are show respectively in Fig.12 (a) and (b). The adaptation operation is performed by mmg tool. Local mesh manipulations are conducted based on the metric field defined on the original mesh nodes. On the other hand, for gmsh, the same metric is used as a background field, in which the BL part is not considered. Given the unstructured nature of the background mesh, Gmsh can only follow roughly the mesh size trend but not reproduce the same element size distribution as shown in Fig.12. Current remedy consists in performing subsequent inviscid volume mesh adaptation illustrated by Fig.5, especially considering Mach number is a more straightforward parameter for shock and wake description. Future work will focus on establishing background metric field that is more adequate for Gmsh kernel.

5 Conclusions and perspectives

The present work provides an end-to-end framework for unstructured mesh adaptation and generation in the context of viscous flow simulation. Following an initial mesh construction with BL, isotropic mesh adaptation can be performed with or without BL. While the inviscid volume mesh adaptation, which is realized thanks to mmg tool based on a newly defined metric field, is more classic, a new procedure, namely adaptation-remeshing, is introduced for mesh adaptation with BL.

Figure 11: Boundary layer mesh illustration on the cross section of the aircraft wing after four tetrahedra mesh adaptation iterations, (a) global view, (b) zoom at the leading edge, (c) zoom at the trailing edge.

Such procedure, which relies on the robust BL mesh construction, avoids specific local mesh operations on semi-structured elements. The proposed framework is validated through empirical tests on Onera M6 and CRM configurations. First results demonstrate its efficacy on shock and wake induced flow feature capturing.

Future work is threefold. Firstly, as discussed in the previous section, a more adequate background metric field should be designed with respect to Gmsh kernel. Second, parallel mesh generation and adaptation functionalities are necessary for more scalable applications. Last but not the least, the BL mesh generation algorithm should be tested on more configurations involving more complex geometrical features.

Figure 12: Adapted mesh within the ninth adaptation cycle (a) after adaptation, (b) after remeshing.

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